

POTATO PRODUCTIVITY DEPENDING ON THE INFLUENCE OF GROWTH REGULATORS**Trembitska O.,***Candidate of Agricultural Sciences***Herts M.,****Mazur D.,****Kanarskyi O.,****Kruk K.,****Serhiychuk G.,****Yarko M.***Master's degree**Polissia National University, Ukraine***ABSTRACT**

One of the most effective ways to utilize plant reserves is to use a method of regulating its functions with the help of plant growth regulators. At the present stage, the requirements for an agricultural worker are not only limited to quantitative production, but also to high-quality and economical use of energy resources. Of course, the use of mineral and organic fertilizers is an indisputable fact in increasing crop yields. However, due to the country's financial situation, their use has significantly decreased. Therefore, traditional energy-intensive technologies must be replaced by fundamentally new technologies and farming methods.

The country is launching the production of new complex preparations with a wide range of effects on various crops. And there are already highly effective, multi-faceted preparations for individual crops. New generations of genetically safe plant growth regulators have already been synthesized, which allow us to create effective ecological systems and, as a result, maximize the productivity of plants, animals and microorganisms.

In our research, we studied the possibilities of optimizing the growth, development of plants, and ecological purity of products through the use of plant growth regulators on potatoes in the agroecological conditions of Peremoha LLC, Korosten district, Zhytomyr region.

Keywords: potatoes, nitrates, growth stimulants, biosil, poteytin.

Statement of the problem. Producing agricultural products, including potatoes, in volumes that would satisfy the needs of people for food and animals for feed requires new energy-saving technologies and techniques, and the introduction of biological farming. In addition, it is necessary to make fuller use of the potential of the plants themselves [5].

One of the most effective ways to use the reserves of a plant organism is to use a method of regulating its functions with the help of plant growth regulators. At the present stage, the requirements for an agricultural worker are reduced not only to quantitative production, but also to qualitative and economical consumption of energy resources. Of course, the use of mineral and organic fertilizers is an indisputable fact in increasing crop yields. However, due to the country's financial situation, their use has significantly decreased. Therefore, traditional energy-intensive technologies must be replaced by fundamentally new technologies and farming methods. The scientifically based application of technology elements using plant growth regulators not only increases yields but also enhances plant resistance to disease and stress factors, reduces fertilizer and pesticide application rates, and reduces the content of heavy metals and nitrates in crop products. The production of such products is constantly being improved, taking into account various requirements: increasing yields, reducing costs, reducing the anthropogenic burden, etc.

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For example, potato growth stimulant Poteytin stimulates the growth and development of potato plants, increasing their yield by 35-80 c/ha. It significantly improves the quality of tubers, increases the content of starch and vitamins. Increases resistance to diseases and adverse weather factors [3].

Promotes thickening of leaves and stems, reduces damage by the Colorado potato beetle and late blight.

Studies indicate a positive effect of Triman on the growth and development of cereal grains. Its effect on the biosynthesis of stress proteins in the roots of winter wheat seedlings is noted. The drug increases plant resistance to low temperatures, facilitates the transfer of high temperature periods by plants [1-3].

Pre-sowing treatment of grain (12 hours) with this preparation activates the synthesis of heat shock proteins and enhances the synthesis of low molecular weight polypeptides. Spraying of winter wheat with Triman significantly increases the grain yield by 10,3-12,6 c/ha, the protein content is 10,65% against 9,28 in the control, gluten 25,13% against 20% in the control variant.

Klymenko T. V. and others [2] prove that the joint use of growth regulators with fungicides in the pre-sowing treatment of winter wheat seeds makes it possible to significantly reduce (by 25% or more) the consumption rates of treatments without reducing the bioprotective effect with an increase in yield and improvement of its quality. Estimates show that only by reducing the consumption rate of Roxyl from 1.5 kg per

1 ton of seeds (the regulatory rate) to 1 kg/t when used in combination with Emistim C (10 ml/t), the cost of purchasing Roxyl per 1000 ha is reduced by UAH 2000. With a total area of 12 million hectares under spiked grain crops in Ukraine, currency savings could amount to about USD 50 million.

Long-term trials of emistim C and agrostimulin in different soil and climatic zones of Ukraine have shown that they increase the resistance of wheat plants not only to diseases and pests, but also to other stress factors such as drought, low temperatures, and soil salinity. For example, winter wheat plants from seeds treated with emistim C on a number of farms in Chernihiv Oblast survived the winter of 1996-1997, while crops from untreated seeds froze out on the same farms.

For potatoes, the most effective growth regulator is poteytin. The drug was studied on more than 30 varieties in specialized institutions in Ukraine, Latvia, and Poland [6,7]. Most of the tested varieties were sensitive to the drug. Almost all varieties showed increased plant viability, increased resistance to adverse climatic factors, stress, reduced incidence of viral diseases and damage by the Colorado potato beetle, wireworm, improved biochemical composition and marketable quality of tubers [7,8,9].

The use of growth regulators is also cost-effective because they can be applied to vegetative plants or seeds simultaneously with other chemicals.

In agricultural production, plant growth stimulants are most commonly used to treat seed material. But there are other ways to use them as well.

Growth stimulants are more commonly used on cereals and to a lesser extent on potatoes and vegetables. At the same time, the potential of these compounds as regulators of plant growth and development to increase yields makes it possible to use them much more widely.

The aim of the research. To study the effectiveness of different doses and types of plant growth regulators on potato productivity, the level of pollution in

the agro-ecological conditions of LLC "Peremoha", Korosten district, Zhytomyr region.

Research methods. The experiments were set up in 4 replications in accordance with GOST 46.23.74.

The replications were arranged in one tier, with systematic variants. The total area of the plot is 50 m². Our experiments were laid out according to the following scheme:

Scheme of the experiment

1. Control (without BAR)
2. Biosil - 15 ml/ha
3. Poteytin - 15 ml/ha

The fertilizers studied according to the scheme of the experiment were applied under spring plowing at a dose of 40 t/ha of manure + N₉₀P₈₀K₉₀.

Potato planting rate was 30 c/ha. Potatoes of the Luhovska variety were used in the experiment. This variety was bred at the Institute of Potato Growing of the Ukrainian Academy of Agrarian Sciences.

Medium-ripening, table-quality Taste is good. It has high field resistance to late blight, macrosporiosis and the most common viral diseases. The tubers are oval, light pink, with superficial eyes. The skin is smooth, the flesh is white and does not darken during cooking. The starch content is 15-16%. The yield in some plots was more than 500 c/ha. It is well stored.

Fertilizers in the experiment were applied: organic in the form of semi-rotted manure in doses of 40 t/ha, mineral fertilizers were applied N₉₀P₈₀K₉₀ in the form of ammonium nitrate, simple granular superphosphate, magnesium potassium.

Research results. Potatoes respond well to fertilization, especially organic fertilizers, but the best fertilization system for potatoes is the combined application of organic and mineral fertilizers. According to the results of our research on the combined application of mineral fertilizers in the treatment with different types of growth stimulants, we obtained the following results (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Potato yield depending on growth regulators, t/ha (average for 2020-2022).

The highest yield was obtained in the Poteytin variant, namely 21.4 t/ha, which is 34,5% higher than the control, while the yield was slightly lower in the Biosil

variant, which was 18,7 t/ha, which is 20,6% higher than the control. But the lowest yield was obtained in the control, which amounted to 15,5 t/ha.

It should be noted that the growth regulator Poteytin, which is a mixture of Emistim C and Agrostimulin, is more influential on potato plantings, which is confirmed by the results of many studies [8, 9].

According to the results of our studies on the qualitative composition of potato tubers, we noted that there is a tendency to increase the content of starch and dry matter when plants are treated with growth regulators (table 1).

Table 1

Influence of growth regulators on potato quality, %.

<i>N^o</i>	<i>Variants</i>	<i>Dry matter content</i>	<i>Starch content</i>
1	Control (without BAR)	18,8	13,3
2	Biosil	20,3	14,2
3	Poteytin	20,8	15,5

Thus, the highest starch content was obtained in the Poteytin variant, which was 15,3%, which is 16,5% higher than the control, slightly lower than the Biosil variant, which is 6,8% higher than the control. Almost the same trend was observed in the dry matter content, which was 20,3-20,8%.

One of the most important conditions of today is to obtain environmentally friendly agricultural products, so in our research we decided to study in detail the effect of growth regulators on the accumulation of nitrates in potato tubers (table 2).

Table 2.

Nitrate content in potato tubers depending on the type of growth regulators (average for 2020-2022).

<i>N^o</i>	<i>Variants</i>	<i>MPC</i>	<i>Nitrate content, mg/kg</i>	<i>Deviation from control</i>	
				-	%
1	Control (without BAR)	120	97	-	-
2	Biosil	120	72	25	26
3	Poteytin	120	63	34	35

Poteytin contributed to the lowest accumulation of nitrates in potato tubers: the nitrate content was 35% lower than the control. The use of Biosil resulted in a 26% reduction in the nitrate content of the products.

Thus, the involvement of these preparations in potato processing made it possible to reduce the nitrate content from 26 to 35%.

Conclusion. In the agro-ecological conditions of Polissya of Ukraine on sod-podzolic soils with low NPK content, to improve the basic agrophysical, agrochemical, biological properties in the soil, increase productivity and improve the quality of potato tubers, we recommend to farms of different ownership systems the use of the biologically active growth regulator Poteytin, on the background of 40 t/ha of manure + N₉₀P₈₀K₉₀, which increases potato yield by 34,5% and significantly reduces the level of nitrate pollution of agricultural products.

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